

Need of Women Health in the Working Place

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Abstract

The well known truth is 'women are the hub source of any society and the home'. Hence, it is observed that women's expectations are pronounced as – they want to be treated as intellectually appreciated, psychologically recognized, economically independent, socially equal and physically comfortable. Of course, these all above expectations are common need of all humans without any gender disparity. In this economic revolutions or compulsive need of developing society, it is required that women should contribute in all types of services and employability globally. Comparably, the health conditions and health issues are not same for both the gender. Obviously, women have different and complicated anatomy. Hence, health issues of women are different and more than the men physically. Since, the role of women is important in any organization, it is more important to consider their health issues and to solve their problem expressively. This paper explains the need of women health in the working place with its challenges to solve them briefly.

Introduction

"If you check the health of women, you check the health of society"

-Rebecca Milner

Female human have her different anatomy than male human. Obviously, the degradation of health of female human has more than the male human. Undoubtedly, the relaxation and sudden mood changing capacity of woman is lower than the man due to many reasons like opportunity, culture, availability, acceptance level and birth characters and societal limitations. Hence, the health condition is the major issue in the development of women in all aspects. Even though, a woman is intellectually confident and emotionally matured, her health condition is being noticed and criticized in different dimension both personally and academically. In this case, it should be accepted that some constitutional rights and relaxation should be provided by the working management and the organization literally. Some of the organizations are being providing such things, the execution is not up to the mark of expected level in the working place of the women to some extent.

Causes of Women's Health Issues

- Hereditary Reasons: Parental health condition and the genetic reasons may cause their health issues before the old age. Due to

- birth giving and hormone imbalance in later, it leads a great issues among their survival abruptly
- **Medicinal Reasons:** At the time of birth itself, some of them have critical limitations in having food, types of food, quantity of liquid items, salt and sugar level consumption, periodic and compulsive medicines. It may cause some health issues when they are growing up significantly
 - **Food Habits:** Depends on the cultural backgrounds, the intake of foods and drinks may cause some bodily defecting nature of the persons. The effect of those things will be influenced in their health slowly
 - **Over Workload:** Due to poverty, single parenting, diverse parental care, some of them have gone more and hardworking compulsion without any proper food and sleep. These effects will lead their reaction at the time of adulthood undoubtedly
 - **Improper Sleeping Habits:** Many of them are not having ideas on importance of proper sleeping. Especially, women are poor sleeper right from the child age. Girl child may not be allowed to sleep more hours than opposite gender due to many reasons. This may continue after childhood due to many responsibilities. This will make the result of health issues at the adulthood definitely
 - **Pollution:** Healthy environment is not only meant for providing air, water and land with its cultivate quality, it has to provide proper air, water and security without degrading its purity, and it provides assurance for the next generations for their living comfortably. If not, it will diminish the life of living things unhealthy
 - **Political Demonstration:** Good policy and its effective implementation of norms and laws for the welfare of human in general, women in particular are in hand of stable political governance. If not, it may cause the stress among the living people in respective state of country. This may definitely cause health condition distress among the momen without any doubt.
 - **Un-employability:** If the scope of employability is changing, the literacy rate of people may also diminish; because of the opportunities is lagging or simply scope less, the attitude towards educations and training may come to slow down in general. This may cause a tremendous impact on women empowerment.
 - **Migration:** Due to political reasons, war in the county, natural disaster, for having higher education and parent occupational transfer, children being migrated from one place to other. In these cases, the adaptability is the major issue among the children especially to girl children to their level of comfort and environmental satisfaction. This leads a notable change and effects among them with respect to their emotional balance and its causes some health related issues to some extent.
 - **Sexual Harassment Fear:** Sexual harassment is one of the important causes widely happening with different dimensions. This makes the girls/women to have poor confident in the societal activities in general and in the working place in particular. If the emotional and security confident are absent, women are easily affecting and it will reflect on their health predominately.

Expectations of Women in the Working Place

Women are the motivating force to make the process and activities productively. They are the tools to make the systems perfect and are the corners to turn the concern zenith. Hence, a working woman coming to any job is not only for earning money and also mark her role in that concern as effective and to prove her role concretely. She requires the following some expectations in the working Place: She is..

- expecting to accept the criticism without notifying the gender disparity
- expecting the interactions without considering their health conditions and physical appearances
- expecting to provide a healthy working environment without biasing
- expecting to consider their productive suggestions offered by them

- expecting appreciation without coding their gender particularly
- expecting to avoid comparison personally
- expecting to interact in official language
- expecting to consider their health issues equally if need arises
- expecting to provide and maintain a good sanitary facilities
- expecting to provide sexual-harassment-free and sexual-abuse-free environment

At present, women are achieving more in sports, defense, police and security throughout the world especially in eradicating the concept of ‘weak physical structure and fear of facing struggle’. Empowerment of women is the concept wise fully successful but implementation level is in still progressive. It is not meant that women still have not received opportunities and rights; it is not enough to make their efforts and availing their efficiency to the greater level.

Requirements of Emotional Health among Women in the Working Place

It is observed that emotional agitations would lead to achievement blocking among women especially. Hence, working place should be made with appropriate assurance in providing emotional confident, physical comfort, societal recognition, and gender equality so as to make use of women source in the productive outcomes of any working organization effectively.

Now-a-days female children are not given proper security to the required extent in terms of emotional, intellectual, economical and socially contributive at earlier stage. Also, they are facing sexual harassment situations too additionally in this developed society. Obviously, it is the big question arises as ‘what is the state of women employers in the working place?’ It should be noted and the security should be provided to them in terms any sexual abuse and harassment legally by considering their role and importance in the working place in all levels. Respect is not a materialistic honours to the women, it is an emotional confident is being provided from the opposite sex in the working place and it should be realized meaningfully. If an emotional support and appreciation are being given to them, the personal and organizational achievement and their productivity will reach a great level productively.

Challenge of Women in the Working Place

A woman is having more complications anatomically, but, she has to have some living challenges in the working place.

- She should satisfy the level of expectation in their working place equally
- She should overcome the gender issues by focusing the achievement individually
- She should provide the confident behaviour in achieving the goal
- She should avail the academic opportunities without any hesitation
- She should avoid the unexpected situation without omitting other’s suggestions
- She should maintain the self-respect without losing her business bondage
- She should make to understand her views with authentic evidences for further development
- She should hold appropriate data based information for further clarification ever
- Finally, she should have good dress code depends upon the working place appropriately

It is noticed that only few percentages of women can reach their achievements in different fields. It is also accepted that their health issues may not be considered or noticed by the authority positively to the greater extent. It is not meaning that they are not considered, they may not be known or realized to some expected level.

Position of Women Empowerment with respect to Women's Health

Our society is now being making the women dependent throughout their lifestyle in for many reasons. As ratification, in order to give security and natural need of cultural bondage of women, such type of dependency is unavoidable in the society. Of course as safety aspect, women are being protected and they are not notable much enough if they affected by any health issues in the working place. This is nothing but the need of realization of bodily issues or issues comes due to aging and other genetic or challenged nature if any. The requirement of privacy in the working place is more important for women than the other gender. In observation, equal works are being done and completed by all with equal financial benefits specifically in higher level working culture. But, it is not happening so for in middle or low level without any proper employment papers with its regulations legally. In this context, it is not mean that women empowerment is achieved to great extent totally without considering the overall population of women in any society. In addition to security in working place, there should be moral acceptability and emotional respect with respect to their health and physical conditions of women. By fulfilling all these hidden expectations or requirements of women in the working place, we may talk about the level of women empowerment and status of women empowerment successively.

Conclusion

“To call women the weaker sex is a libel; it is man's injustice to woman. If by strength is meant moral power, then woman is immeasurably man's superior” -M K Gandhi

According to Gandhi, a woman is the companion of man, gifted with equal mental capacities. She thereby has the right to participate in the very minutest detail in the activities of man and has an equal right to freedom and liberty with him. But, she is entitled to a supreme place in her own 'domain' or sphere of activity.

Even though women are given equal importance in the life of human being contextually, still, women are facing many problems and crisis in their life span, viz., sexual harassment, inequality, avoiding educational opportunities, absence of vocational training, unequal salary if working opportunity provided, and unhealthy criticism with respect to their physical and social aspects, so on. Facing all such hurdles, women are now part and parcel of development of societal progress in all fields without any doubt. But, working place is one of the important domains in making their work effective. In this context, health issues associated with women are not avoidable things. Hence, it is important to make them convenient if they are affected by any health issue at their working place. It is not a big task to implement; it requires some attitudinal changes among the co-workers in the working place. It is not the required demand from the working organization; it is the emotional request of women to make their part productive in the working place so as make their role productive.

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